

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Rab14 (UniProt ID: P61106) for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Abstract

Rab14 is a member of the Rab small GTPase family that regulates autophagy, endosomal recycling, and membrane transport between the Golgi apparatus and endosomes, thereby influencing cellular processes such as cytokinesis, cell polarity, and migration. Here we have characterized five Rab14 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

P61106, *RAB14*, Rab14, Ras-related protein Rab-14, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation

Introduction

Rab14, a member of the Rab small GTPases superfamily, governs endosomal recycling and membrane trafficking between the Golgi and endosomal compartments (1). It facilitates the fusion of autophagosomes and lysosomes (2), regulates membrane trafficking events during cytokinesis (3), directs polarized membrane trafficking in epithelial cells (4), and supports the formation of intercellular junction in migrating cells (5). In cancer cells, Rab14 contributes to tumorigenesis by promoting cell proliferation, migration and invasion (6-8).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (9). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein (9). Here we characterized five commercial Rab14 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Rab14 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (10) and in Table 3 of this data note (9).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines (11). In the absence of commercially available KO cell lines suitable for imaging and that express sufficient levels of the target protein, siRNA technology can be employed to knockdown (KD) the target gene (12, 13). To determine which cell line demonstrates high expression of Rab14 and thus be appropriate for KD, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify cell lines that express the target at levels greater than 2.5 log₂ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (14). The *RAB14* transcript is expressed at 5.8 log₂ TPM+1 in DMS 53 and this cell line was therefore selected for antibody testing. A non-targeting control siRNA pool was used to treat DMS 53 control (ctrl) cells, while *RAB14* was KD using a pool of siRNA targeting this gene.

To screen the five antibodies by western blot, ctrl and *RAB14* KD protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all five Rab14 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of the five antibodies to capture Rab14 from DMS 53 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific Rab14 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

In conclusion, we have screened five Rab14 commercial antibodies by western blot and immunoprecipitation by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human DMS 53 ctrl and *RAB14* KD cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (14). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect Rab14 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study Rab14 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Rab14 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot and immunoprecipitation are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (9). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (15, 16). To knockdown *RAB14*, DMS 53 cells were treated with the *RAB14* SMARTPool from Horizon Discovery (cat. number L-009934-00-0005) for five days. DMS 53 control cells were treated with the ON-TARGETplus Non-targeting Control Pool (Horizon Discovery (cat. number. D-001810-10). Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 13778030) was used to transfect the siRNA following the manufacturer's protocol.

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21429 and A-21424). Peroxidase-conjugated anti-mouse IgG for IP detection is from Abcam, cat. number ab131368.

Antibody screening by western blot

DMS 53 ctrl and *RAB14* KD cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at

room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

DMS 53 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels. Anti-mouse IgG for IP:HRP was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.3 µg/ml when mouse raised antibodies were used for both IP and western blot.

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank -GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	CRL-2062	CVCL_1177	DMS 53	WT

Table 2: Summary of the Rab14 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
ABclonal	A12752	5500008142	AB_2759597	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.49	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP1-84720	000044514	AB_11045393	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb, IF
Proteintech	15662-1-AP	00006950	AB_2173630	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.27	Wb
Proteintech	67953-1-Ig*	10020923	AB_2918705	monoclonal	3G7B3	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-37735*	ZF4352655	AB_2897659	monoclonal	1779CT6 92.32.86	mouse	0.50	Wb

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence, *= monoclonal antibody

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Figure 1: Rab14 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: Rab14 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Rab14 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of DMS 53 ctrl and *RAB14* KD were prepared, and 35 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Rab14 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of ctrl and KD lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: A12752 at 1/1000, NBP1-84720 at 1/1000, 15662-1-AP at 1/1000, 67953-1-Ig* at 1/5000, MA5-37735* at 1/2000. Predicted band size: 23.8 kDa. *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: Rab14 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

DMS 53 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated Rab14 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the anti-Rab14 MA5-37735* used at 1/2000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. *= monoclonal antibody.